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Goal-setting as a condition for professional self-development of Master's students in Teacher Training Programme

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Abstract

Students' orientation towards mastering a teaching profession determines their goal-setting, as well as the course of professional and pedagogical self-development. Disclosure of the relationship between these processes functioning is aimed at creating conditions in learning environment that contribute to the subsequent self-realization of a pre-service teacher. The purpose of the study is to clarify the interdependence between the goal-setting of pedagogical magistracy students, their need and readiness for professional self-development. The study was conducted at the Kazan Federal University (Russia) among 153 first-year undergraduates. It was found that at the beginning of training, about 40% of students have goals that correspond to teaching, and for the majority of students (57-63%), regardless of whether they received pedagogical education before, goals are diffuse (ambiguous). Presence of pedagogical experience predetermines goal-setting of students to obtain a pedagogical profession. Regardless of the specifics of goal-setting, self-development needs of pedagogical magistracy students are actively implemented. It was found that among students whose goals correspond to teaching, the partial readiness for professional and pedagogical self-development is higher, even among those without previous pedagogical education. This applies to motivational, gnostic and communicative components of professional self-development. The undergraduates showed a reliably ($P \geq 0.95$) higher readiness for self-development of the ability to analyze pedagogical activity, accumulation of experience in self-educational activity, cooperation in professional self-determination. It is concluded that goal-setting, aimed at teaching, can be considered a condition of high readiness for professional and pedagogical self-development. It is assumed that goal-setting management will contribute to activation of professional self-development.

Keywords: pedagogical magistracy, students, goal-setting, self-development, partial readiness for professional self-development.

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Introduction

In the modern system of higher education, close attention is paid to the development of the ability to set goals as a significant quality for successful professional and personal self-realization (Samsonenko, 2019). Clearly perceived goals during the period of university studies predetermine systematic professional development and self-development of a student. At the same time, the process of personality self-development is aimed at achieving professionally and personally significant goals (Garanina, 2016). The relationship between the processes of goal-setting and self-development becomes obvious, when the formulation of perceived goals is more vivid in the process of personal self-development, and the goal-setting ability is the basis for predicting high results of self-development. In addition, the components of self-development are considered as a factor in the professional growth of future teachers (Ivaniuk et al., 2020).

In higher pedagogical education, motivation for mastering a future profession contributes to the transformation of goals, which outwardly formulated by a master's student, into internal personal needs and beliefs. This transformation determines the course of subsequent professional and pedagogical formation and development. When preparing students for a pedagogical magistracy, it is important to diagnose the goals of students, their need and readiness for professional self-development in order to create conditions for an educational environment comfortable for subsequent self-realization in teaching, project, and research activities.

Purpose and objectives of the study

In the current study, the focus of our attention was the problem of setting goals during professional training of master's students in pedagogy at Kazan Federal University. The purpose of the work was to clarify the relationship between the goal setting of undergraduates and their need and readiness for professional and pedagogical self-development. To achieve this, it was necessary to correlate goals that are significant for students with their readiness for subsequent pedagogical activity, to determine their actual need for self-development, as well as partial readiness for professional pedagogical self-development. The survey involved 153 students of the 1st year of study (2019-2020 and 2020-2021). Among the respondents there were those who consistently (without time gaps) study the programs of pedagogical education (bachelor's and master's degrees), as well as students who have experience in teaching after completing the first level of higher pedagogical education. In addition, for some of the respondents pedagogical magistracy is the only education connected with teaching (they have not received pedagogical education before).

Literature review

Meeting the needs of student's personality in self-development and self-realization is an essential feature of the modern educational paradigm. One of the main questions of self-development is goal-setting (Grevtseva et al., 2018). The philosophical view presupposes the understanding of goal-setting from the point of view of the perspective nature of individual's activity (Khakhalova, 2015). Goal-setting is also defined as an intellectual and creative activity to define and formulate goals (Egorova, 2016).

Goal-setting as a pedagogical phenomenon is associated with setting goals and objectives in professional activity and ensures the development of a professional career. Foreign researchers propose to consider goal-setting as a factor influencing and ensuring student achievement (Moeller et al., 2012; Abe et al., 2013; Schippers et al., 2020). Khutorskoy (2011) points to the "competence of educational goal-setting". By applying the goal-setting theory to explore different aspects of student career orientation, it was found that it is partially related to the professional development (Clements & Kamau, 2018).

Goal-setting is considered as a system of changes management, as a mechanism for the development of students' professional self-awareness (Kardovskaya, 2011), as a mechanism for the formation of their motivation in preparation for professional activity (Kuchina, 2011). There is an opinion that goal-setting is an integral part of self-development along with value orientations, self-esteem, reflective and motivational-volitional components (Nevolina, 2015). Malm (2009), studying teacher education from the point of view of professional development, suggests that teacher training programs should be a good balance of development of cognitive and emotional sides of future teachers.

Enumerating student's goals in the field of professional self-development, Egorova (2015) distinguishes "development of a professional orientation" and "formation of readiness for professional activity". Earlier, we found that when studying for a master's program, students' readiness for professional self-development increases due to motivational, moral-volitional components and the ability to self-government in pedagogical activity (Asafova & Vashetina, 2020). However, there has not been revealed the interdependence between individual characteristics of professional self-determination, goal-setting, the need and readiness for professional self-development of future teachers. The disclosure of these interrelations will help in systematic creation of conditions for professional and pedagogical development of students during their preparation for subsequent pedagogical activities. This can ensure the management of goal-setting as a systemic process that unites all the activity components of a personality (Saraskina & Vaschenko, 2014) and will contribute to activation of self-development.

Methodology

In carrying out the work, we used the methods of testing, analysis and comparison of the obtained results.

To study the features of goal-setting, diagnostic methods based on self-assessment were used (Nieskens & Sieland, 2001) to clarify orientation and readiness of undergraduates for pedagogical activity. Students were asked to choose those answers of closed-end questions that they correlate with the goals and desires in the profession. In addition, some of the answers were more consistent with the orientation towards pedagogical activity, the other part, on the contrary, towards non-pedagogical professions. Other empirical methods included diagnostics of the realization of self-development needs (Fetiskin, Kozlov & Manuilov, 2002, p. 311) and diagnostics of partial readiness for professional self-development in education (Fetiskin et al., 2002, pp. 311–313). The latter methodology is a self-assessment map of readiness for self-educational activity and allows self-assessment of self-development formation in a number of components: motivational, cognitive, moral-volitional, gnostic, organizational, communicative, as well as the ability to self-government. A feature of this diagnosis is the inverse relationship between the number of points that the respondent gains in the course of self-assessment and his readiness for professional self-development (the less points one gets, the higher his readiness is, and vice versa). The obtained data were processed using the methods of mathematical statistics. Statistical significance was assessed by the Student's t-test ($P \geq 0.95$).

Results

The results obtained when correlating goals significant for students with their readiness for further pedagogical activity indicate that only 39.6% of respondents have orientation towards teaching profession (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Correspondence of students' goal-setting and their orientation to the teaching profession.

The rest of the undergraduates have predominantly diffuse (unclear) goals at the beginning of their studies in the pedagogical magistracy (57.6%) (Fig. 1).

Moreover, in both samples, there are up to 70% of students with pedagogical education that they received at the previous level of higher education, but without teaching experience. Only a very small proportion of first-year students of the pedagogical master's degree (2.8%) have goals that can be connected with alternative (non-pedagogical) professions.

When analyzing the goals of undergraduates belonging to different groups in terms of presence/absence of teacher education and experience in teaching, the following differences were established. The majority (up to 63%) of respondents have diffuse (unclear) goals, and for 37% of the respondents, the goals correspond to the orientation towards obtaining a pedagogical profession and self-realization in it (Fig. 2). The obtained data characterizes different groups of students: with pedagogical education and experience in teaching, with pedagogical education but absence of teaching experience, without pedagogical education.

Figure 2. Distribution of goals for different groups of students: with pedagogical education and experience in teaching experience, with pedagogical education but absence of teaching experience, without pedagogical education.

However, in the group of students with pedagogical education and teaching experience, there predominantly (more than half) expressed the goals corresponding to teaching profession (Fig. 2). Consequently, it is the experience of pedagogical activity that affects the goal-setting of students of a pedagogical magistracy.

It has been determined that students studying in a pedagogical magistracy actively realize self-development needs, as indicated by the sum of points scored by students in accordance with the assessment scale (Fetiskin et al., 2002). No significant difference was found in realization of these needs among the students of the groups we identified above (Table 1).

Table 1. Realization of self-development needs by students of pedagogical magistracy.

Groups of students	Goals correspond teaching profession	Diffuse goals
Pedagogical education + pedagogical experience	61±2,74	62,8±2,22
Pedagogical education +	61,1±2,07	61,6±2,21
Pedagogical education -	58,7±1,98	63,2±1,3

During the experimental work, we stated that in the groups of students indicated above, the readiness for professional and pedagogical self-development is not the same. This is typical, first of all, for students whose goals correspond to the implementation in teaching. There are no significant differences between the groups of students with pedagogical education and teaching experience (Fig. 3). However, a higher readiness for professional self-development was established for students without pedagogical education at the previous levels of education (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Partial readiness for professional self-development of undergraduates whose goals correspond to teaching (* $P \geq 0.95$, ** $P \geq 0.99$).

As for the components of partial readiness, a difference was diagnosed in the ability to analyze pedagogical activity (1), synthesize and generalize (2), accumulate and use the experience of self-educational activity (3), as well as to cooperate in professional pedagogical self-determination (4) (Table 2). These components characterize a higher readiness among students without pedagogical education, but with goals corresponding to teaching activity.

Table 2. Components of partial readiness for professional and pedagogical self-development among undergraduates whose goals correspond to teaching.

Groups of students	Gnostic component		Communicative component	
	1	2	3	4
Pedagogical education + pedagogical experience	7,7±0,4	7,6±0,3	8,1±0,3	8,2±0,2
Pedagogical education +	7,5±0,3	7,6±0,2	7,6±0,3	7,9±0,2
Pedagogical education -	6,4±0,3**	6,5±0,3**	6,5±0,3*	6,6±0,4**

Note: 1 - ability to analyze pedagogical activity, 2 - ability to synthesize and generalize, 3 - ability to accumulate and use the experience of self-educational activity, 4 - ability to cooperate in professional and pedagogical self-determination; * $P \geq 0.95$, ** $P \geq 0.99$.

When comparing the indicators of readiness for professional self-development among students with pedagogical education, a higher value of the motivational component was revealed in case the goals contribute the implementation in teaching, compared with a group of students with diffuse goals. In general, if the goals of students are characterized by diffuseness, ambiguity, then the differences between all three groups of students are not expressed.

Discussions

The work shows that about 40% of students of the pedagogical magistracy have goals that correspond to obtaining the profession of a teacher (Fig. 1). At the same time, for the majority of undergraduates of the 1st year of study, the goals are characterized by diffuseness (ambiguity), even for students who received a diploma in teacher education at the previous level of education (up to 63%) (Fig. 2).

This situation will not contribute to identification of needs and interests to be satisfied during formulation of goals by students (Zhukova, 2015). In addition, according to domestic researchers, up to 40% of students often do not independently determine goals, which subsequently leads to insufficient motivation (Kabanova & Shkunova, 2018). Kardovskaya (2011) in her work concludes that the mechanisms of goal-setting among students are not sufficiently developed, this prevents the development of professional self-awareness. In our opinion, the diffuseness of goals can be determined by the fact that many students do not have a sufficiently clear idea of pedagogical activity due to the lack of independent pedagogical experience. They master educational programs at different levels of higher education without a clear goal-setting for subsequent self-realization in the teaching profession. Our results indicate that it is the presence of pedagogical experience that is an important condition for students (more than 50% of respondents) to formulate goals correlated with teaching (Fig. 2).

Goal-setting as an indicator of pedagogical orientation formation predetermines professional self-development of an individual. Having the same realization of the needs for self-development (Table 1), undergraduates of the 1st year of study revealed differences in the partial readiness for professional and pedagogical development (Fig. 3). These differences are clearly manifested in groups of students whose goals correspond to the teaching profession. The highest partial readiness was noted in the group of students without previous pedagogical education. It can be assumed that it is the conscious interests and needs of these students for subsequent self-realization in pedagogical activity that contribute to an increase in readiness for professional self-development. Partial readiness for professional and pedagogical self-development of a future teacher can be understood as readiness for self-development in terms of changing various components of professional activity (motivation, ability to independently organize their own activities, communicative competence, level of moral and volitional qualities, etc.) (Kiseleva & Soloviev, 2017). In the present study, undergraduates showed a higher readiness for self-development of abilities to analyze pedagogical activity, accumulate experience of self-educational activity, cooperation in professional self-determination (Table 2). In our opinion, this again indicates the decisive role of goal-setting for the professional and pedagogical self-development of an individual.

Conclusion

When clarifying the interdependence between the goal-setting of students receiving teacher education, their need and readiness for professional and pedagogical self-development, it was found that most of them have diffuse goals at the beginning of training. The diffuseness of goals may indicate, in our opinion, the absence of a clear prospect for self-realization in the teaching profession. Pedagogical experience of undergraduates is crucial for formulating goals that are consistent with a pedagogical activity.

It is confirmed by the results we received from students without previous pedagogical education, whose goals correspond to the implementation in teaching, that a higher readiness for professional and pedagogical self-development was noted in a number of components and subcomponents. That is readiness to develop the ability to analyze pedagogical activity, accumulation of experience in self-educational activities, cooperation in professional self-determination. Therefore, goal-setting, corresponding to implementation in the teaching profession, can be considered a condition of a high readiness for professional and pedagogical self-development.

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